

ECOTOURISM OPPORTUNITIES OF THE OHANGARON VALLEY AND THEIR RESEARCH ON THE BASIS OF GAT

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Abstract: Ohangaron Valley has diverse landscapes and rich resources for the development and promotion of ecotourism. However, ecotourism sites have not been well studied so far. The purpose of this study was to model and identify ecotourism objects by combining methods of Slope, Visibility, Topographic Roughness Index, NDVI, Hilshade, NDSI based on Geographic Information System (GIS). It was developed based on six criteria, including geographic location, slope, roughness index, snow appearance analysis, settlements, lakes, terrain. The results showed that about 26.19% were highly fit, 35.34% were moderately fit, 25.28% were fringe fit and 13.17% were not fit. Most of the areas with high unsuitability were in the southeast, southwest, and mountainous regions in the north, and the most unfit areas for ecotourism development were in the south.

Keywords— Ohangaron, ecotourism, underground, surface, ArcGIS, route, tourist zone, NDVI, Visibility, index.

INTRODUCTION

When thinking about the organization of travel to the embrace of nature, the term "ecotourism" is often mentioned. In fact, ecotourism is, on the one hand, a rapidly growing branch of the tourist market, and on the other hand, it is a system based on the positive impact of man on nature. In addition, it is an integral part of the tourism infrastructure and is not only an idea, but also a specific type of general tourism. Its impact on the environment can be different (negative, neutral and positive).

Ecotourism is widely used in the modern management of reserve areas and natural parks. The reason for the rapid growth of this type of tourism on a global scale is not only the deterioration of the environment, but also more and more popular places for recreation - mountain resorts, warm sea shores, plains and forests. it is also being exploited.

Ohangaron Valley occupies the central and southeastern parts of Tashkent region. It is located between 68050' - 70035' east longitude, 40040' - 41015' north latitude. The studied area decreases from 3716 meters to 260 meters from the source of the Ohangaron river to its confluence. It was determined that the study area occupies an area of 6558 km² using GAT programs (Arcmap, QGIS, ArcGIS Pro) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Geographical location of the research area.

The research area is bordered by the Kurama Mountains in the east, the Chotkal Mountains in the northeast, the Chirchik River Basin in the north and northwest, and the Syrdarya Valley (Dalvarzin Desert) in the south. Snow-capped mountain, landscape and climatic beauty, National Park and wildlife sanctuaries, rich biodiversity, ethnic and socio-cultural diversity, pilgrimage and holy places and adventure tourism activities attract national and foreign tourists.

Due to its geographical location, the valley has favorable opportunities for economic and social development. At the same time, it is worth noting the uniqueness of its natural geographical location. The topography of the valley is varied, and one can see the combination of plains, hills, slopes and

mountains. Kurama and Chatkal mountain ranges created unique climate and natural scenery. The climate of the oasis is sharply continental, but in the mountainous regions of the valley, summers are cool and winters are colder than in other regions. The Ohangaron Valley area is located in the interior of the mainland, far away from the seas and oceans. Its effect can be seen in the low amount of precipitation, sharp differences in temperature and humidity, short but dry spring, and long and dry summer. Various Central Asian landscape types can be found in the valley. For example, the western plain part of the valley is made up of sandy, barren and salty desert landscapes, large areas of the plain and mountainous regions of the southeast are occupied by cultural landscapes, and the west is occupied by the oasis landscapes of the Syrdarya valley.

Today, Ohangaron Valley is a region with favorable natural geographical conditions, economic potential, and qualified labor resources for large-scale development of industrial and agricultural sectors. Based on this, it is now necessary to effectively use natural resources in this area, to increase the intensity of irrigated land, to improve farming culture, to increase the productivity of agricultural crops, as well as to produce high-quality, ecologically clean, competitive products for the world market. attention should be paid.

The territory of the valley is unique from a geographical point of view, it includes sandy deserts, salt marshes, oases, mountainous plains, low and moderately high mountains. The uniqueness of the natural conditions of the region can be seen in the economic activities of the population. The richness of various landscape types of the valley region was naturally the main factor in the development of the territorial division of labor, and natural economic sectors were formed accordingly. For this reason, animal husbandry, horticulture, beekeeping, dry farming, recreation and tourism are developed in the mountain and sub-mountain areas, and cotton and grain are mainly cultivated in the old and newly developed lands in the plains.

The convenience of the economic geographical location of the valley creates good opportunities for its socio-economic and cultural development. It is located in the most developed city of Tashkent, the compact location of the territory is one of the important features of its economic geographical position. This condition has a positive effect on the development of the economy of the valley and allows for economically efficient use and convenient management.

The hydrographic network is unevenly distributed in the Ohangaron valley. There are almost no rivers and streams in the plains. On the contrary, the river networks are well developed due to the high rainfall in the mountainous regions. The amount of water, mode and branching of the existing rivers and streams also depend on the geographical conditions.

To achieve the objective of the study, necessary spatial, non-spatial data and existing maps were collected from primary and secondary sources. A Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) digital elevation model (DEM) with a spatial resolution of 30 ms was used to analyze topographic aspects

such as slope and topographic roughness index. Evaluation and prediction of ecotourism opportunities consists of three stages: creation of geospatial database, selection and preparation of ecotourism object, and verification and interpretation of the result (Validation criteria). Factors such as site identification, slope, terrain roughness, vegetation cover, drainage, visibility, accessibility, rural settlement, habitat, elevation, climate, proximity to groundwater and lakes were considered to assess ecotourism potential. The slope of the land is of great importance for creating ecotourism opportunities. A low slope of the land is required for the construction of ecotourism facilities, and an increase in the slope reduces the possibilities of developing an ecotourism facility. The Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM is used for slope generation. A slope layer was generated using SRTM DEM with a spatial resolution of 30 m based on the percentage elevation method:

$$\text{Slope (percent)} = \frac{\text{rise}}{\text{run}} \times 100.$$

The slope layer was classified according to five comfort classes, i.e. very high, high, medium, low and very low, and they cover an area of 76 km², 276 km², 706 km², 1388 km² and 4752 km², respectively. The preferences are assigned according to the relative importance of each class, where a higher value of the slope means less opportunities for ecotourism, i.e. less opportunities for building facilities, and vice versa (Figure 2).

2-rasm. Nishablik(Slope) analizi.

Topographic roughness index (Topographic roughness index) is used to define and express the topographic features of the region, i.e. unevenness in the relief. Topographic roughness is directly related to ecotourism and is widely used for ecotourism potential. A high unevenness of the land surface indicates less opportunities for the development of an ecotourism facility, and a low level of the land is suitable for the development of an ecotourism facility. SRTM DEM(relief)

data is used to calculate the topographic roughness index. The topographic roughness index (TRI) is a relative topographic location index, i.e., calculated based on the land firmness and SRTM DEM(relief) data.:

$$TRI = \frac{SD - MinDEM}{MaxDEM - MinDEM}$$

Here, TRI denotes the Topographic Roughness Index, SD denotes the smoothed DEM of 10 × 10 pixel values, max DEM denotes the maximum (numeric number) value of 10 × 10 pixels, and min DEM denotes the minimum value of 10 × 10 pixels. The value of topographic roughness (TRI) is divided into four classes, i.e., very high, high, moderate, and low, where each zone covered areas of 1029 km², 2918 m², 2703 km², and 854 km², respectively. A zone with high topographic unevenness is unfavorable for the construction of ecotourism facilities, while it indicates a low level of zone comfort (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Topographic roughness index (Topographic Roughness Index).

There is a positive correlation between ecotourism and vegetation density. Ecotourism includes abiotic, biotic and cultural attractions. Among them, biotic features, i.e. biodiversity, wildlife and natural areas are the most important aspects of ecotourism development.

NASA's Landsat 8 imagery was used to calculate Greenness Index (NDVI).:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + R}$$

Here, NIR shows the DN value in the near-infrared range, and R shows the DN value from the red range of the satellite image, and the result of the NDVI value data is further divided into five classes, where the higher value is the higher the ecotourism development of the region. shows the degree of compatibility (Fig. 4.).

Figure 4. NDVI (greenness) analysis

NDVI analysis shows that the area has been divided into comfort classes of undamaged vegetation, moderately damaged vegetation, damaged vegetation, non-vegetated area and they are 426 km², 1836 km², 4197 km², 99 km² respectively. took over.

Visibility of the snow-covered mountain is the most important aspect for the development of ecotourism. The view of snow-covered mountains is taken into account to analyze the comfort of developing an ecotourism facility, and it is positively related to the attraction of tourists as well as the arrival of tourists. Tourists mostly prefer to stay in places with a view of the snow-capped mountain. Spatial analysis of visibility using visibility analysis is based on the height and location of snow-covered peaks. The visible portion of the snow-covered mountain was determined by Visibility analysis, and the results were reclassified into four classes, such as very high, high, moderate, and low suitability, depending on the visibility feature. As a result, an area of 32 km² was divided into a very high comfort class and 423 km², 157 km² and 5946 km² into a high, medium and low comfort class, respectively (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Snow visibility analysis (Visibility).

The nature and diversity of the culture of the people of Ohangaron Valley also attracts responsible tourists to a great extent. Ecotourist prefers to stay in places where cultural interaction with local people is possible. There is a positive relationship between local community culture and ecotourism. Unique cultural features of any region attract tourists from different parts of the country and abroad. The study area has its own cultural characteristics in terms of its traditional value, social customs, language, dress, food habits, religion, etc. At the core of ecotourism is the preservation of local community culture. Thus, priority was given to the selection of rural areas for locating the ecotourism facility in Ohangaron Valley. For this analysis, five buffer zones of rural settlements were created: comfort, subcomfort, discomfort, subdiscomfort, extradiscomfort, and they occupied the areas of 18, 30, 36, 39 and 40 km², respectively. When choosing a place for ecotourism, priority is given to the zone closer to the village, and comfort decreases as the distance increases (Fig. 5.).

Figure 6. Proximity of ecotourism objects to population centers.

Altitude plays an important role in the development of ecotourism, and the increase in altitude has a negative effect on the development of ecotourism. Higher altitude means less potential for human habitation along with reduced oxygen levels. Thus, a lower height indicates higher possibilities for building an ecotourism facility and vice versa. Ohangaron valley is located at an altitude of 300-3700 m above the average sea level. The entire region is divided into four altitude classes: very high (3700–3000 m), high (3000–2000 m), medium (2000–1000) and low (less than 1000 m), and they cover 708 km², 1380 km² respectively. km², occupied the areas of 1800 km² and 2670 km². An area with a lower altitude is suitable for the development of an ecotourism facility, while an increase in altitude reduces the possibility of ecotourism development (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Elevation

The ability to see surface water. Water availability and ecotourism area are positively correlated. The area close to the river basin network shows a high level of convenience for the analysis of ecotourism potential, and the opportunities decrease as the distance increases. Proximity zones were further reclassified into five comfort zones, i.e., very high, high, moderate, low, and very low comfort zones, covering areas of 3,266 km², 1,462 km², 982 km², 541 km², and 309 km², respectively (8 - fig).

Figure 8. The ability to see surface water

The proximity of lakes and reservoirs. In terms of surface water availability and beauty, lakes are of great importance for the development of an ecotourism facility. Four buffer zones have been created to determine the suitability of lakes and they are very high, high, medium, low which occupy 80 km², 86 km², 100 km², 112 km² respectively. (Area of lakes is taken from Diva GIS site) (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Ecotourism facilities near lakes and reservoirs areas suitable for construction.

CONCLUSION

By leveraging cloud technologies effectively, educators can create dynamic and engaging learning experiences for students, whether in traditional pedagogical settings or in the realm of cyberpedagogy.

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